

NOTES

Dioxouranium(VI) Heterochelates

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ALTHOUGH there has been considerable research interest on the homochelates of dioxouranium(VI) very little has appeared on the heterochelates of dioxouranium(VI)¹. In this paper we describe the synthesis and characterization of new dioxouranium(VI) heterochelates, the ligands used being *orthophenanthroline*, 2,2'-dipyridyl, 3-aminopyridine, *orthophenylenediamine*, ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, tetramethylenediamine, hexamethylenediamine and the Schiff base derived from benzoylhydrazide and salicylaldehyde. There has also been considerable research on the Schiff base complexes of first transition series metal ions. But comparatively little work has been reported on such complexes of second and third transition series metal ions^{2,3}. It is hoped that the present study would contribute to the development of the chemistry of heterochelates.

Experimental

Materials: Uranylacetate dihydrate was obtained from Hopkins and Williams (London). Salicylaldehyde, ethylenediamine, *orthophenanthroline* and 2,2'-dipyridyl were the products of Sarabhai M. Chemicals. Trimethylenediamine, tetramethylenediamine, hexamethylenediamine and *orthophenylenediamine* were procured from Fluka AG (Switzerland).

Methods: Uranium analysis was done gravimetrically as U₃O₈ after decomposing the complex with conc. HNO₃ and then igniting. Nitrogen was determined microanalytically. The Schiff base and aromatic amine were estimated quantitatively by bromometric titration technique. Conductance measurements were done in DMSO using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge (type CL01-02A). Mol. wt. was determined by the Rast method⁴ using diphenyl as the solvent. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using a Beckman IR20 spectrophotometer calibrated with polystyrene. Reflectance spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU recording spectrophotometer attached with the reflectance arrangement.

General method of synthesis of heterochelates: A methanolic solution of uranylacetate dihydrate (0.84 g; 0.002 mole in 10 ml) was added to a methanolic solution of the Schiff base (0.48 g; 0.002 mole in 10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a waterbath for 2 hr. To this solution a methanolic solution of the appropriate bidentate amine (0.002 mole in 10 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. The separated precipitates were suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Yield 80%.

Results and Discussion

The dioxouranium(VI) heterochelates have been synthesized by employing a preparative method in which the possibility of expansion of coordination number of the homochelates has been utilised. The heterochelates are formed by the reaction of bidentate ligands on six-coordinated complex of the type UO₂L.CH₃OH (where L = tridentate dibasic Schiff base) prepared *in situ*. It may be noted that the *in situ* method of preparation of heterochelates described in this paper is simpler and less time consuming as it does not require the isolation of the homochelates in the solid state. The heterochelates are of the type UO₂L(AA) (where LH₂ = sal-benzoylhydrazide, AA = *orthophenanthroline*, 2,2'-dipyridyl, 3-aminopyridine, *orthophenylenediamine*, ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, tetramethylenediamine or hexamethylenediamine). The molecular weight measurements indicate that the complexes are monomers. They are non-electrolytes ($\Delta_M = 2.8 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) and diamagnetic as expected for 5f⁰ uranium(VI).

The Schiff base exhibits the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretch at 1668 cm⁻¹ which disappears in the complexes due to enolisation and consequent coordination of oxygen atom. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch of the Schiff base occurs at 1610 cm⁻¹ and this band is lowered by 5-15 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch of *orthophenanthroline*, 2,2'-dipyridyl and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1558, 1582 and 1590 cm⁻¹ respectively^{6,7}. In the heterochelates, this band shifts to higher energy by 10-35 cm⁻¹. This negative or positive shifts in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch is indicative of nitrogen coordination of the Schiff base⁸ and heterocyclic amines⁹. The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ band of ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, tetramethylenediamine, hexamethylenediamine, *orthophenylenediamine* and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1620, 1620, 1620, 1620, 1640 and 1590 cm⁻¹ respectively and in the complexes this band shifts to lower energy by 10-25 cm⁻¹ and in some cases merges with the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch. This indicates coordination through the nitrogen atoms of the

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF DIOXOURANIUM(VI) HETEROCHELATES^{a, b}

Complex	Found (Calcd.)% U N ligand ^c			Mol. wt.	$\nu_s(\text{OUO})$	$\nu_{as}(\text{OUO})$	f_{UO} m dynes/Å	R_{UO} Å	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$
	U	N	ligand ^c							
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(en)	42.15 (41.90)	10.05 (9.86)	41.43 (41.90)	541 (568)	800	880	6.43	1.75	1550	1595
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(tn)	41.12 (40.89)	9.83 (9.62)	41.05 (40.89)	608 (582)	800	880	6.43	1.75	1555	1595
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(bn)	39.75 (39.93)	9.13 (9.39)	39.38 (39.93)	573 (596)	810	890	6.58	1.75	1555	1595
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(hn)	38.06 (38.14)	8.65 (8.97)	37.77 (38.14)	647 (624)	815	895	6.65	1.74	1555	1600
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(phen)	38.49 (38.64)	9.39 (9.09)	56.13 (56.17)	603 (616)	815	895	6.65	1.74	1555	1595
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(dipy)	35.74 (35.84)	8.26 (8.43)	59.40 (59.34)	642 (664)	820	900	6.73	1.74	1545	1600
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(ampy)	39.35 (39.53)	9.12 (9.30)	55.06 (55.15)	584 (602)	810	890	6.58	1.75	1545	1595
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(o-phen)	34.34 (34.59)	8.28 (8.14)	60.49 (60.76)	701 (688)	820	900	6.73	1.74	1545	1600

(a) Abbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, BHZ=benzoylhydrazide, en=ethylenediamine, tn=trimethylenediamine, bn=tetramethylenediamine, hn=hexamethylenediamine, phen=orthophenylenediamine, dipy=2,2'-dipyridyl, o-phen=orthophenanthroline and ampy=3-aminopyridine.

(b) All ir bands in cm⁻¹.

(c) Schiff base and aromatic amine.

amines. The heterochelates exhibit a strong band at 1545-1555 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) and this band is observed at lower energy (1535 cm⁻¹) in the Schiff base. This is indicative of coordination of the phenolic oxygen atoms of the Schiff base. Thus, the Schiff base is behaving as tridentate ligand coordinating through ONO donor atoms. The ir and analytical data alongwith the valence requirement of the metal ion indicate that the Schiff base is acting as a dibasic ligand.

All the complexes exhibit the $\nu_s(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ in the range 800-820 and 880-900 cm⁻¹ respectively⁸. In the complex UO₂(sal-benzoylhydrazide).CH₃OH these frequencies are observed at 830, 910 cm⁻¹. The observed negative shift of the $\nu_s(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ bands in the heterochelates in comparison to the homochelate is due to the increase of electron density on the uranium atom. This causes an increase in the repulsive forces with the non-bonding electrons of the atoms of UO₂ moiety and thus the U-O bond weakens. The force constant (f) values were calculated by the method of McGlynn *et al*⁸ and these values agree well with those reported in the literature^{8,9}. The U-O bond length (R) was calculated using the relation : $R_{\text{U-O}} = 1.08 f^{-1/3} + 1.17$ and R lies in the range 1.74-1.75 Å in agreement with the reported values (1.60-1.92 Å)^{8,9}. The plot of ν_s vs ν_{as} gives a straight line with slope of 1.0 (calculated by the method of least square) and intercept of -80. In case of linear O=U=O moiety with no interaction of the ligands, the ν_s and ν_{as} are related by the equation⁸ $\nu_s = (1 + 2 M_{\text{O}}/M_{\text{U}})^{-1/2} \nu_{as}$

(where M_O and M_U are the atomic mass of oxygen and uranium) which predicts a slope of 0.94. The higher value of the slope and the negative value of the intercept are due to the strong interaction of the equatorial ligands on UO₂ moiety. The complexes exhibit a band in the range 20000-21000 cm⁻¹ due to the ${}^1E_g \rightarrow {}^3\pi_u$ transition typical of OUO moiety.

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